

Early Productive Behaviour, or the Regional and Global Problems with the Terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation.

Report on Global Session 02 at the World Neolithic Congress, Şanlıurfa, 4 - 5th of Nov. 2024

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About the World Neolithic Congress

The World Neolithic Congress 2024 (WNC24, www.worldneolithiccongress.org) took place from the 3rd to the 8th of November at Harran University, Şanlıurfa, and ended with great success and pleased participants. Almost 1.000 participants from 63 countries and 486 institutions participated, with 687 oral presentations and 60 posters in the globally outstanding event. The 4 days parallel 22 global and 23 regional sessions were interrupted by a day of site visits to Çakmak, Göbekli, Gürcü, Karahan, Sayburç, and Sefer Tepeler, united in the regional Taş Tepeler Neolithic Project; pre- and post-congress excursions to sites like Cayönü supplemented the programme. Various Turkish sponsors and authorities very generously sponsored the congress and its supporting events.

The idea for the congress came from Mehmet Özdoğan. In his lifelong efforts in promoting Neolithic research in Turkey and beyond, this great mind reached the understanding that our (supra-) regional perceptions of the Neolithic need new and differentiated perspectives and corporate input from outside

the regional foci: Discussing the different contexts of the globally asynchronous, acyclic and polycentral Neolithisations would not only open up new approaches and allow us to test our research approaches; they would also – by the background of the global view – enable critical re-considerations of the Neolithic and Neolithisation as terms and concepts.

The organisation of the Şanlıurfa Congress, recently taken over by Necmi Karul and colleagues (Figs. 2-3) from Mehmet Özdoğan, was most efficiently supported by Seda Ongun and countless helpers. It paved the way to a new era of Neolithic research: the comparative study of Neolithisations and the global enlargement of the Neolithic research family. While we are witnessing a growing and horrific division globally, this congress has set us on the path of worldwide mutuality and practice in Neolithisation research, perhaps the only step and contribution we as prehistorians can make to counter global alienation.

The positive experience with the congress in Şanlıurfa influenced its Scientific Committee to enthusiastically decide to continue as quadrennial congresses, with the next gathering likely to be held in China. Experiences of the Şanlıurfa congress will be

Fig. 1 Opening concert of the Congress by the Cihat Aşkın Chamber Orchestra presenting Türk Valsleri. (Photo: H.G.K. Gebel)

collected and transferred to the next organisers. Between the WNC congresses, Neolithic workshops, symposia, conferences, and other gatherings with regional or global foci are invited to informally join under the WNC global umbrella for mutual benefit and support, prioritising multilateral, independent, and cohesive cooperation structures. All colleagues in all regions and countries are invited to join and shape the WNC community.

Fig. 2 Necmi Karul presenting his Congress opening speech. (Photo: H.G.K. Gebel)

Despite the problem of many parallel sessions and the constant need for participants to move between the venue's halls, the atmosphere was relaxed. More problematic was the fact that the wide range of topics on offer meant that the participants mainly attended lectures on their own fields of research; the purpose of the congress was to promote global perspectives on the Neolithic among the participants and hearing the discussions in other regions, could therefore only be fulfilled to a limited extent. Nevertheless, the spirit of this unique congress approach came across well and has undoubtedly become a seedbed for future extended global research approaches.

Special events were the Opening Ceremony at Mehmet Akif İnan Conference Hall in Sanliurfa with a Concert by the Cihat Aşkın Chamber Orchestra presenting Türk Valsleri (Fig. 1); the opening speech by Necmi Karul (Fig. 2) with the following Welcome Reception at Hilton Double Tree Hotel on November 3rd; the Reception, Concert and Exhibition at Şanlıurfa

Archaeology Museum on November 4th; the reception at Hilton Double Tree Hotel on November 7th; and two meetings of the Congress' Scientific Committee. Vivid and fruitful exchanges took place among colleagues everywhere outside the sessions (*e.g.* Fig. 4), helping the mutualities in Neolithic perspectives and celebrating academic cohesion.

Fig. 3 Eylem Özdoğan, a Congress Organising Committee member, explains her excavations in Sayburç. (Photo: H.G.K. Gebel)

Ahead of the daily sessions, keynote lectures were presented by Peter Bellwood (on *Becoming Neolithic: the impact of food production on global human population history during the past 12,000 years*, November 4th), Hsiao-chun Hung (on *The emergence of Neolithic life in East and Southeast Asia: expansions, encounters, and new societies*, November 7th), and Melinda Zeder (on *Unpacking the Neolithic*, November 8th). On November 7th, commemorative speeches were held by Mehmet Özdoğan (Acknowledging the pioneers of the Neolithic research in Southeast Anatolia: Bruce Howe, Halet Çambel, Robert J. Braidwood, Barbara Helwing (From Istanbul to Istanbul: remembering Harald Hauptmann (1936-2018), and Joris Peters (Göbekli Tepe and the legacy of Klaus Schmidt in research on the Early Neolithic in Anatolia).

The Global and Regional WNC24 sessions (Table 1) were held during the intense four days of

lecturing at Harran University's Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences (for the abstracts, please consult www.worldneolithiccongress.org/assets/files/WNC2024-E-Abstracts%20Book.pdf).

Global Sessions: Global Perspectives on the Neolithic

- G01 - Understanding 'Long Neolithics' in Global Comparative Perspective
 G02 - Early Productive Behaviour, or the Regional and Global Problems with the Terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation
 G03 - Foraging to Food Production and The Consequences: A Global Review
 G04 - Population Dynamics in Pre-state Farming Societies
 G06 - Climate Change as a Pacemaker of Neolithic Cultural Change: Global Perspectives
 G07 - Neolithic Processes in the Tropics
 G08 - Biomolecular and Stable Isotope Windows on Lifestyles, Environments and Evolution in the Neolithic
 G09 - Putting Domesticates in their Place
 G10 - The Palaeolithic Antecedents of the Neolithic Revolution: Insights from Hunter-Gatherer Archaeobotany
 G11 - Choices versus Dietary Imperative: Food Circulation Pathways in the Neolithic
 G13 - The Spread of Farming and Herding in Different Parts of the Globe
 G15 - Bioarchaeological Perspectives on the Neolithic Transition
 G18 - The Impact of Neolithic Architecture – the Emergence of Human Built Environment
 G19 - Reading the Stones, Tracing the Changes: Lithic Technology during the Paleolithic - Neolithic Transition
 G20 - Animals in Symbolic and Ritual Items Across the Neolithic World
 G21 - Icons in Transition. The Role of Signs and Symbols During the Great Transformation
 G23 - The Neolithic in Art. Iconography and Society in the First World Agricultural Communities of Eurasia
 G24 - Treating Dead Bodies in the Neolithic: Exploring the Increasing Social Complexity
 G25 - Gifts from the Earth – Interpreting Polished Stone Tool Biographies and their Symbolic, Social and Economic Impact in the Neolithic
 G26 - On People, Tools, and Plant Foodways: Defining new Proxies for the Neolithisation(s)
 G27 - Neolithic clay tokens and other counting objects
 G28 - Geological and Tectonic Influences on Neolithic Societies: Interdisciplinary Insights into Landscape Evolution and Human Adaptation

Regional Sessions: Regional Perspectives on the Neolithic

- R01 - Pathways of Pastoralism: The Dispersal of Herding Practices in Neolithic Southwest Asia
 R02 - Before the Neolithic: Epipalaeolithic and Mesolithic Communities in Anatolia and Surrounding Region
 R03 - Unravelling the Knot: Network Approaches to the Study of the Neolithic Transition in Southwest Asia and Beyond
 R04 - Socio-economic and Symbolic Changes During the PPN-PN Transition in the Near East (7th millennium cal. BC): Paces, Causes and Processes
 R05 - Death, Ritual and the Social Transformations in the Near Eastern Neolithic

- R06 - New Paradigms in the Study of the Neolithic of Central Anatolia 20 Years after the First Synthesis
 R07 - Epipalaeolithic and Early Neolithic Hunter-Gatherers in the Eastern Taurus Foothills
 R08 - The Evidence of Violence in the Neolithic Buildings of Southeastern Turkey and its Possible Relations with Other Regions
 R10 - From Zagros to Alborz and Beyond: Formative and Adoptive Neolithic Lifeways on the Iranian Plateau
 R11 - The Neolithic of Southern Levant in its Wider Context
 R13 - From the "Civilization of minds" to Obsidian Mirrors: the Study of the World Neolithic According to Petr Charvát and Güner Coşkun
 R14 - Regional and Inter-Regional Palimpsests of Neolithisation Processes: South-Eastern Europe
 R15 - The Neolithic of the Aegean and Beyond: Supra-Regional Networks and Local Communities
 R16 - Anatolia and the Balkans During the Neolithization Process: Connections, Similarities and Differences
 R17 - Early Monumentality and Social Differentiation: Transformation in Europe
 R20 - Submerged Neolithic Sites Around the Mediterranean and Europe
 R22 - The Caucasian Neolithic
 R25 - The Dawn of the Neolithic in Northern Eurasia: Development of Foraging Complexity

Table 1 Global and regional Sessions present at the World Neolithic Congress, Şanlıurfa, 4-5th Nov. 2024. (Source: www.worldneolithiccongress.org/sessions.aspx)

Fig. 4 Off-session exchanges. From right to left: Jian-ye Han, Mehmet Özdoğan, Peter Bellwood and Hans Gebel. (Photo: Hsiao-chun Hung)

Protocol of Global Session 02: On the Regional and Global Problems with the Terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation

In his workshop introduction, Hans Gebel stressed that the designation 'early productive lifeways' appears to overarch/ bridge many gaps and avoids fallacies that the terms "Neolithic/ Neolithisation" provide to the research of many cultures in the Americas, Australia, East Asia, Southeast Asia and others. The terms obstruct or distort concepts of their own right that these cultures require. Using the rather neutral concept of 'early productive lifeways' (*sensu* a socially and territorially confined productivity: cf. Table 5) would open paths for respecting their own

cultural identities and developments. However, he asked: Is it really necessary for us to change the term Neolithic/ Neolithisation? Or should we strive for regional re-definitions of these terms, which adequately capture the beginning of the productive/ food-producing lifeways globally? Also, the continued use of the terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation *per se* would be a constant reminder of the adversity and fallacy danger of these terms, which regional re-definitions could counter. Substitute terms for ‘Neolithic/ Neolithisation’ would only reveal the danger that other non-holistic applicability problems arise, especially if we now want to consider global perspectives.

Other topics of his introduction were the Neolithic Ethos (“Neolithisation created a new social phenotype, the Homo neolithicus, or the productive human ruling the globe until today.”); Neolithisations steered by climate change, natural disasters, human-induced depletion/ collapse of environmental systems; and the main characteristics and research state of world’s major Neolithisation centres. He concluded his introduction by presenting his Shared Traits of Global Neolithisations (Table 5).

Fig. 5 Speaker scene from Global Session 02. From right to left: Chao Zhao, Frédérique Brunet and Cédric Bodet. (Photo: H.G.K. Gebel)

Of the 15 session presentations¹, seven covered the session theme from regional and supra-regional perspectives; the others presented research history (2), neuroscientific (1), and research- or concept-critical (5) approaches. The following paragraphs offer a highlight-type characterisation of the session and should not be understood as a report on the session’s content.

The two contributions to research history elucidated the difference between Childe’s term ‘neolithic’ and its current reception as ‘Neolithic’ (Maxime) and reflected on the globally differing understandings of the ‘Neolithic Eve’ based on the diversifying and complex “objective” archaeological data, and the “subjective” methods and perspectives of archaeological school thought (Tabarev and Popov). Unfortunately, only one contribution from cognitive

science (Criado Baodo, Martínez and Verdonkschot) explored the possibilities of approaching the humanities concept of a ‘domestication of mind’ from a cognitive and neuroscientific perspective; this approach assumes that the symbolic and economic systems of the Neolithic can be reconstructed with the help of their “neurological footprint,” among other factors.

One of the conceptual or concept-critical contributions questioned, among other things, if the ‘otherness’ of the late hunter-gatherers is not founded in our “modern (colonial)” perspectives and if the Neolithic transitional role granted to *e.g.* Ohalo II or Natufian sedentism does not reflect common features of modern hunter-gatherers (Finlayson). Another concept-critical contribution – also criticising colonial ingredients in the hunter-gatherer concepts – challenged specifically “broad heuristic and dichotomous classifications like those of (complex) hunter-gatherer societies, showing that foraging and producing are not opposed to each other” (Schreiber).

Perspectives from Çatal Höyük allow to criticise that our Neolithic categories and concepts cannot meet Neolithic heterogeneities; “antifragility and bifurcation” were asked to be included in the concepts for understanding the short-lived Çatal Höyük phenomenon in the “globalised” Neolithic of Southwest Asia (Marciniak). Seen from the production/ re-production perspective, it was criticised that the “total reshuffling of the reproductive structures through the opening of marital unions to the outside world (‘complex-type’), that is, beyond the inner community”, is ignored by Neolithic research (Bodet, Fig. 5).

Our attention was also brought to the kite subsistence strategies challenging existing foraging/ producing dichotomies (industrial/ surplus harvesting and hunting), reported for Southwest, Central Asia, the prairies of North America and by the Ummayad paintings of the 8th CE in Qusayr Amra (Rollefson).

The seven session contributions on Neolithic/ Neolithisation terminology related to regional/ supra-regional Neolithics of Central Asia, China, Japan, Northern Africa, Sicily, Cyprus, and the Northern Levant. Central Asia witnessed distinct Neolithisation processes diverging from the models commonly accepted in the Near East, always accompanied by ongoing foraging in various forms and shares; an ever-adaptive and shifting range of mobility strategies and patterns targeted the productive use of steppes and (irrigated) agricultural land (Brunet, Fig. 5).

The “sporadic” findings of pottery, polished stone tools, and domesticated crops in Northern China – dated between 15000-9000 BP – must be viewed as the “embryonic period of the constituent elements” of China’s Neolithisation, while the period of 9000-7000

BP, characterised by “nucleated sedentary villages and a more intensified exploitation of local resources”, must be regarded as the final establishment of Neolithic lifeways (Zhao, Fig. 5). New evidence from the large site of Nanzuo (600 ha) dating to the Late Neolithic calls for an examination of the Chinese Neolithic from an urban perspective, here represented by the earliest evidence of a “palatial” city centre shortly after 5000 BP (Han).

While stating that the term Neolithic “has come to function as a global term that provides a measure of the transition from hunter-gatherers to early farmers” and herders, Y. Nishaiki presenting the Japanese Jōmon Culture asked if a Neolithic without domestication is not fundamentally questioning the standard definition of the Neolithic.

Peoples’ migrations bringing Neolithic traits to North Africa did integrate local cultures; coastal regions often show delayed or only partial absorption of Neolithisation due to the permanently available marine resources, causing restricted connectivity to productive behaviour (Samira). While a partially similar feature is reported from the Neolithisation of Sicily (Speciale, Lo Vetro, Collina, Forgia, Iovino, Gulli, Bazan, and Giannitrapani), recent excavations at the Uzzo and Kronio cave sites have raised the question of whether the island has also witnessed possible “middle ground” socioeconomies sharing traits of the Mesolithic and the early to middle Neolithic (7000-5000 cal BCE).

The contribution on the Halaf and ‘Ubaid periods – “characterising the interconnectivity that brought people, materials and ideas into networks of relationships across a wide region” and creating “tensions between interconnectivity and cultural identity” – “critically evaluated the utility of applying exogenous Neolithisation criteria to regions whose enthusiasm for the Neolithic experiment seems to have been, at best, ambivalent.” (Wasse and Clarke).

Monday, 04 November 2024

Hans Georg K. Gebel: Introduction to the Session: Early productive behaviour, or the regional and global problems with the terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation

Felipe Criado-Boado, Luis Martínez, Jadranka Verdonkschot: Cognitive and neurological bases of the domestication of mind

Bill Finlayson: Searching for a beginning

Maxime Brami: Childe’s ‘Neolithic Revolution’ and its relevance to the archaeology of Southwest Asia

Gary Rollefson: Neolithic food production hunting technology in arid landscapes across the world

Andrey Tabarev, Alexander Popov: “Neolithic Eve”: Personal view on the local and global perspective

Tanja Schreiber: Neolithic hunter-gatherers? Rethinking “Neolithic trajectories” through a Siberian case study

Chao Zhao: When Neolithic began in North China: A debate on divergent interpretations of the Early Neolithic

Cédric Bodet: Production and Reproduction: the mingled infrastructures of the Neolithic Social (R)evolution

Frédérique Brunet: Long-Term Neolithisation Processes in Central Asia: The Key Role of Mobility, Territories and Interactions

Tuesday, 05 November 2024

Alexander Wasse, Joanne Clarke: Choice in the face of change. How ‘Neolithic’ were Cyprus and the Greater Syrian Desert in the 7th and 6th Millennia BC?

Hamil Samira: The Neolithic in Northwest Algeria

Arkadiusz Marciniak: The Central Anatolia Neolithic – a globalization perspective

Yoshihiro Nishiaki: Is the Jōmon culture “Neolithic”?

Jian-Ye Han: New discoveries at Nanzuo site and the dawn of early state in the Loess Plateau, China

Claudia Speciale, Domenico Lo Vetro, Carmine Collina, Vincenza Forgia, Maria Rosa Iovino, Domenica Gulli, Giuseppe Bazan, Enrico Giannitrapani: New insights on the cultural, social, and economic domestication of Sicily

All Participants: Final Session Discussion: Lessons for future regional and global Neolithic research

Table 2 Lectures presented¹ in Global Session 02 of the World Neolithic Congress, Şanlıurfa, 4-5th Nov. 2024 (Session Organiser: Hans Georg K. Gebel).

Global Significance of Neolithisation: Protocol of Global Session’s 02 Final Discussion

The final discussion aimed to elaborate on the session’s key takeaways, provided by the participants’ final statements from the perspectives of their research areas. Initially, four topics were suggested to be considered by participants in their statements:

- 1) The supra-regional and global significance/ insignificance of Neolithic achievements,
- 2) the adaptations in subsistence practices, social developments and/ or cognitive developments to climate shifts and
- 3) explaining compatibility problems using the ‘classical’ definitions of Neolithic/ Neolithisation in their research areas.
- 4) Possible comments on the Neolithic legacy and lessons: Are lessons to be learned from your region’s Neolithic pasts relevant for our present and future?

In his introduction to the Final Discussion, Hans Gebel again stressed that the applicability problems with the terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation occur not only with societies at the border of/ with origins in (confined) productive lifeways in the Americas, Australia, Central and East Asia, Southeast Asia and others. They also became a matter of debate for the tremendous Neolithic diversities identified in Neolithic ‘core areas’ like the Fertile Crescent and beyond. He advocated again to pave ways to redefine or update the terms Neolithic/ Neolithisation from global perspectives and by including extended anthropological (*i.e.* etho-ontological) parameters that apply worldwide (*cf.* Table 5), without therefore

cancelling the terms Neolithic/Neolithisations: “All is about changing the box content, not its label.”

Referring to his session introduction, Gebel stressed that Neolithic ‘productive lifeways’ – *i.e.* ‘sustainable’ socially, territorially and ideologically confined productivity aimed at food and other security and (partly excessive) growth – appear to be the connecting and common feature of all global Neolithics. He considered the concept of ‘food-producing lifeways’ quite worthwhile but less appropriate since it does not reflect the likewise decisive cognitive shifts established with these lifeways.

Gebel also referred to the exemplary table presented by T. Schreiber, in which she listed 20 names of ‘surrogates’ for late hunter-gatherer societies at the Neolithic border (Table 4): This compilation nicely documents – as another impactful element in Neolithic research – the extent to which personal research foci and dispositions influence terminologies. Furthermore, he warned against the fallacies of the “foraging/productive” dualism directly or indirectly influencing our Neolithic categorisations and our understanding of the mixed expressions between productive foraging and foraging productivity. An additional argument referred to Neolithisations of islands/ isolated areas and coastal regions (the contributions of C. Speciale *et al.* and H. Samira) and their particular conditions in receiving/ absorbing the Neolithic traits rather than developing them autochthonously.

Session presenters offered the following key takeaways:

Gary Rollefson stated that “the term Neolithic is used out.” He argued that the term should be replaced with the term domestication and used extensively, covering all resources, *e.g.*, the domestication of landscape, water, labour, etc.

Bill Finlayson explained that the problem with the term arises from the habit in Neolithic research to totalise everything as a package, which does not allow us to encompass all the diversity in the Neolithic process. Thus, he advocated for an ontologically oriented redefinition of the Neolithic, employing niche construction theory and seeing the multiple trajectories towards the Neolithic as an accumulation of hunter-gatherer innovations which in turn gradually modified the people involved.

Cédric Bodet largely supports the understanding of the Neolithic through socio-economic concepts rooted in the Marxist tradition and proposes to advance this direction by considering the impact of social relations of reproduction on Neolithic social structures. Testart and Malinowski’s ethnological analyses of hunter-gatherer and incipient agricultural societies have shown the importance of kinship patterns, marital issues, and the growth of lineages as a primary social entity. Applying these concepts to

Southwest Asian Neolithic societies, he proposed to revisit key archaeological issues, such as the emergence of dualist symbolism, the question of pre-domestic agriculture among Göbekli Tepe and other early Neolithic societies, the probable advent of a PPNB bride-price system, and the constitution and abandonment of mega-sites.

Frédérique Brunet stated that a redefinition of the Neolithic must consider the appropriation of territoriality by societies on their way to becoming productive, in conjunction with the development of long-distance cultural interactions, further exemplifying this by the long-term shifts between dry-farming pastoral communities in the steppes and settled irrigated oasis agriculture in Central Asia.

Yoshihiro Nishiaki pointed out that domestication is not necessarily a prerequisite for Neolithic life, as demonstrated by the Jōmon Neolithic of Japan, which otherwise exhibits all the Neolithic characteristics.

Felipe Criado-Boado, Jadranka Verdonkschot and Luis Miquel Martínez Otero proposed decoupling the Neolithic and domestication, framing them in terms of mind and cognitive changes rather than solely biological or subsistence-based interpretations. This is supported conceptually, theoretically, and empirically, as shown by recent advances in Neo-, Meso- and Palaeolithic archaeology. If an equivalence between Neolithic and Domestication is maintained, the Early Neolithic should be placed as early as the Palaeolithic. However, treating them as independent processes, as suggested by the authors, the Neolithic emerges from the densification of earlier domestication practices, characterised by productive lifestyles and demographic growth. Domestication, from the Indo-European root *domus* (Latin) and *domos* (Greek), signifies integrating the wild into the domestic sphere or extending the domestic into the wild – or both. The Neolithic, therefore, reflects the amplification and complexity of these practices. The domestication of the mind, in turn, represents the adaptation of human cognition to this “Neolithic mode,” a key shift that involves understanding how concepts were tamed. This approach aligns with findings from the ERC Synergy Grant project XSCAPE about Material Minds, exploring the cognitive dimensions of these transformations.

Alexander Wasse explained that despite there being as many ways of studying the Neolithic as there are researchers specialised in the Neolithic, it is notable how narratives have, on occasion, all found it useful to construct explicit or implicit dichotomies, ranging from the empirical to the metaphorical. While few would dispute the assertion that there is a continuum of economic behaviours, with hunters at one end and farmers at the other and all sorts of hybrids in

between, there is some evidence to suggest that the overarching ontological principles that differentiate food-collecting from food-producing societies may be mutually exclusive. He believes that it is these principles – rather than the behaviours they give rise to – that offer the best route to understanding Homo neolithicus.

Not Neolithic?	Neolithic?
Hunting and gathering	Agriculture and herding
Sharing	Owning
Egalitarianism	Stratification
Mobility	Sedentism
Group	Household
Integration	Segmentation
Situation	Realisation
Propitiation	Alienation

Table 3 Potential ‘Neolithic’ attitudes and behaviours, and their ‘non-Neolithic’ counterparts: Implicit dichotomies, ranging from the empirical to the metaphorical? (Compilation by Alex Wasse, presented at WNC24’s Global Session 02)

A few ideas drawn from the anthropological literature are therefore appropriated below in order to construct a dualistic metaphor as a handrail to interpretation and, hopefully, to encourage further discussion. We may consider the extent to which these principles would have been codependent within their particular sides of the metaphor, with the attenuation of one impacting the viability of the ontology as a whole. By looking at the process of Neolithisation in this way, ideology and economy emerge as two sides of the same multifaceted metaphorical coin, encouraging us to adopt holistic approaches.

Arkadiusz Marciniak also considers the Neolithic a subject of domestication of mind and prefers an ontological definition of it. Furthermore, he suggested that the Neolithic, namely, the urban aggregation centres, must be understood from its end.

Tanja Schreiber, who was not present at the Final Discussion, later contributed the following statement to the protocol: Hunter-gatherer cate-

gorisations largely depend on individual researchers’ research perspectives and focal points. For instance, terms like ‘resource-rich hunter-gatherers,’ ‘non-affluent hunter-gatherers,’ or ‘delayed-return societies’ (Table 4) often arise when focusing on economic inequality. Conversely, analyses of social inequality yield terms such as ‘socially stratified hunter-gatherers’ or ‘hierarchical hunter-gatherers.’ These terms typically address cases where hunter-gatherer lifeways deviate from the traditional, progressivist narrative of egalitarian, highly mobile, small-group societies, reflecting an effort to accommodate the diversity of non-agrarian lifeways. At the same time, this terminological diversity reveals colonial and evolutionist patterns of thought that continue to shape perceptions of hunter-gatherer societies and Neolithisation. While farming and animal husbandry are often framed as progress, forager groups are reductively categorised into dichotomies such as ‘simple’ versus ‘complex,’ which call for critical evaluation. To achieve a global understanding of Neolithisation, we thus must also interrogate our terminologies and research paradigms.

Maxime Brami, who was not present at the final discussion, later delivered this statement to the protocol: We often forget that the adjective Neolithic was traditionally uncapitalised, referring to a universal stage of production in Vere Gordon Childe’s *Man Makes Himself* (1936). Aside from food production, M. Brami believes what we now call Neolithic has little in common with Childe’s initial concept of “Neolithic societies”. Childe’s ideas for agricultural origins were mostly based on comparative ethnography, such as Malinowski’s work among the Trobrianders, rather than Southwest Asian prehistory, whose research was still in its early stages.

Hamil Samira, not present at the Final Discussion, later contributed the following statement to the protocol: The Neolithic marked the pivotal step of humankind that led to potential stability and group for-

Table 4 Examples of terminologies used to differentiate hunter-gatherer groups that deviate from the ‘small-scale, mobile, and egalitarian band model’. (Compilation by Tanja Schreiber, presented at WNC24’s Global Session 02)

Shared Traits of Global Neolithisations (Draft: Hans Gebel, state by 20241116)

Could reformed and holistically grounded Neolithic research that includes etho-ontological (i.e. an extended anthropological) approaches allow for a global re-definition of Neolithic/ Neolithisation and the continued use of both terms?

The problem of understanding: We are not “speaking” the same terminologies and concepts in and outside our areas.

However, we dare: Can the following features of ‘a global Neolithic’/ the world’s early productive lifeways characterise – in specific selections and combinations/ blends – regional and supra-regional Neolithisations?

- general but highly diversified shifts from foraging to socially and territorially (including ideologically confined productive lifeways (includes productive foraging?))
- (different scales of) food production and food security are the dominant features of early productive lifeways, mostly (reciprocally) associated with all sorts of (partly excessive) growth, while parallel foraging may continue
- acyclic, asynchronous, multicentric and partially reversive/ stagnant processes and transitions
- supra-regional and regional blends of early productive ingredients that could establish variable productive lifeways/ socio-economies,
- occur in polycyclic, polycentral, polyfactorial, and polycasual trajectories behaving seemingly autochthonous/ erratic, interactive, spreading/ diffusing, and mixed
- all aiming for food/ consumption and territorial security (securing stagnancy or growth)
- creating conditions for material and intangible agglomeration/ aggregation, acceleration and other progressive/ excessive mechanisms, or at least stagnant sustainability
- social differentiation and hierarchisation, ending in some regions with urban developments/ stratified societies
- cognitive frameworks with confined (i.e. group-self) oriented reciprocities,
- additional and higher levels of internal and external conflict due to establishing productive territorialities and/ or defending them
- not necessarily are (initially) related to sedentary territoriality or supply storage
- nature itself becomes an ultimate means of (surplus) productivity (with depletion risks)
- show greater vulnerability when exposed to climate change or natural disasters
- have the capacity to survive/ establish? as modern Neolithic lifeways until today once conditions apply

Do global perspectives on the Neolithic support a/ the foraging-productivity dichotomy/ dualism? (‘Polarity’ of the early Neolithisations?)

To what extent are the Neolithic/ Neolithisation characteristic for our modern production behaviour? Are we still of the social phenotype Homo neolithicus?

Table 5 List of potentially globally valid properties of Neolithic /early productive lifeways. (Compilation by Hans Gebel, initially presented as a slide at the Final Session of WNC24's Global Session 02, amended version)

mation bound to land. While the phenomenon varies from region to region, and various parts of the Middle East pioneered incipient sedentarisation, this process encompassed most of the Mediterranean countries at the latest by the sixth millennium; the Saharan grasslands witnessed food production since the 9th millennium BCE (African Humid period). The understanding of this period should be based on more than merely material cultural evidence but should focus on the lifeways.

Andrey Tabarev, not present at the Final Discussion, later added the following statement to the protocol: The global Neolithic/ Neolithisation cannot be understood without considering the primary abiotic raw materials the cultures and their toolkits depended on: flint and other lithic materials. In some soil environments, worked stone artefacts are often the only source of information on crafts and subsistence.

Claudia Speciale et alii consider that the terms 'Neolithic' and 'Neolithization' still retain their validity and are globally understood, despite potential ambiguities. The challenge is to frame the processes we aim to document when discussing the last hunter-gatherers and producer societies. Regarding the concept of 'domestication of the mind,' the fields to explore are, above all, anthropological (e.g., Lévi-Strauss, etc.) and sociological (e.g., Weber, Durkheim, etc.) for a redefinition of archaeological data. This is not a simple task.

Grotta dell'Uzzo remains a key site, but it is essential to emphasise that it is a cave not far from the coast and cannot be representative of the whole region.

In a final remark, Hans Gebel offered to continue the session’s Final Discussion, based on its protocol, to promote it further and encourage non-participants to join the redefinition of the Neolithic from a global perspective. This might also help cover the session’s geographical and epistemic/ heuristic gaps and provide a broader approach to the session’s publication. He concluded that this would follow and support the spirit and aims of the World Neolithic Congress initiative, immediately interested in promoting global perspectives in Neolithic terminologies.

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Endnote

¹ Session contributions by Julian Thomas (on The Neolithic as an assemblage), Alison Betts (on Foundations and Neolithic dispersals across Asia: Some comparative considerations), Xiaoran Wang (on Reassessing regional economy during the Neolithization: Nevalı Çori and Yumin from the Fertile Arc of Western and Eastern Asia), and Mingjian Guo (on The Neolithisation in Northwestern Hebei Area, China) were cancelled for various unfortunate reasons.